

CLINICAL-PATHOGENETIC FEATURES AND RISK FACTORS OF RECURRENT BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN

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To identify and analyze the clinical features of the course of recurrent bronchitis in children, pathogenetic mechanisms, and the main risk factors leading to the development of the disease

ABSTRACT

Recurrent bronchitis is one of the most common forms of respiratory diseases in children, characterized by the recurrence of bronchitis episodes at least 2–3 times a year. The disease most often occurs in preschool children, which is explained by the functional immaturity of their immune system and increased sensitivity to external environmental factors. Frequent recurrence of recurrent bronchitis leads to the formation of a persistent inflammatory process in the bronchial mucosa, impaired mucociliary clearance, and increased bronchial hyperreactivity. These conditions, in turn, increase the risk of developing chronic bronchopulmonary diseases, including bronchial asthma. Therefore, it is important to study the clinical and pathogenetic aspects of this disease and identify the main risk factors.

Introduction

Recurrent bronchitis is one of the most common forms of respiratory diseases in children, characterized by the recurrence of bronchitis episodes at least 2–3 times a year. The disease most often occurs in preschool children, which is explained by the functional immaturity of their immune system and increased sensitivity to external environmental factors. Frequent recurrence of recurrent bronchitis leads to the formation of a persistent inflammatory process in the bronchial mucosa, impaired mucociliary clearance, and increased bronchial hyperreactivity. These conditions, in turn, increase the risk of developing chronic bronchopulmonary diseases, including bronchial asthma. Therefore, it is important to study the clinical and pathogenetic aspects of this disease and identify the main risk factors.

Research objective

To identify and analyze the clinical features of the course of recurrent bronchitis in children, pathogenetic mechanisms, and the main risk factors leading to the development of the disease.

Research materials and methods

The study was conducted retrospectively on the case of children diagnosed with recurrent bronchitis who were under observation in the pediatric department. The clinical condition of the patients was studied in detail, the duration and nature of the cough, shortness of breath, increased body temperature, auscultatory changes (dry and wet wheezing) were assessed. When collecting the anamnesis, the child's frequent respiratory infections, family

allergic history, exposure to passive smoking, and the ecological state of the living environment were taken into account. Laboratory tests included a complete blood count, eosinophil count, and inflammatory markers (C-reactive protein). The type of nutrition (natural or artificial) was also assessed as a risk factor.

Results and discussion

According to the results of the analysis, a long-lasting and frequently recurring cough was identified as the main clinical sign of the disease in children with recurrent bronchitis, which was often wet in nature. Auscultation revealed scattered dry and wet wheezing, and in some patients, signs of bronchial obstruction. Laboratory tests showed that in some patients, an increase in the number of eosinophils indicated the presence of an allergic background, and a moderate increase in the level of S-reactive protein indicated the ongoing inflammatory process. Pathogenetically, respiratory viral infections are the leading factor in the development of recurrent bronchitis, and their frequent recurrence leads to damage to the bronchial mucosa and a weakening of local immune defense. Analysis of risk factors confirmed that passive smoking, adverse environmental conditions, allergic predisposition, and artificial feeding play an important role in the development of recurrent bronchitis.

Conclusion

Analysis of risk factors confirmed that passive smoking, adverse environmental conditions, allergic predisposition, and artificial feeding play an important role in the development of recurrent bronchitis.

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